

SEGÓBRIGA, SPAIN

8 SEPTEMBER 2022, ATHENS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 818496. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Introduction

1. Lessons learned: Challenges

Challenges

Lessons

Strong and cohesive group of stakeholders

Allocate sufficient efforts for stakeholder engagement

Lack of statistical data at the municipal level

look for mechanisms to improve the systematic compilation

Policy makers work his parcel.
Break routines and barriers

be open to other options

1. Lessons learned: Changes in our region

BEFORE

Resources underutilized
New performance tools

NOW

LEADER only considered policy
More political and financing options

EUROPEAN
REGIONAL
DEVELOPMENT
FUND

Diputación
de Cuenca

1. Lessons learned: Changes in our region

BEFORE

**Stakeholders working
individually**

**Stakeholders know each
other and work in
coordination**

NOW

1. Lessons learned: Recommendations

TIME

**ASSERTIVE AND
PARTICIPATORY
ATTITUDE**

**Technical
assistance**

2. Main Results achieved

Multi-stakeholder collaboration

YEAR	Policy	Rural Community		Rural Newcomer		Scientific	TOTAL
		Female	Male	Female	Male		
2019	15	2	7	1	3	2	30
2022	16	6	14	1	4	6	47

New insights and knowledge about Segobriga region

Resilience & Vulnerable

Indicadores | Tabla/Mapa/Gráfico

Estructura de Indicadores

- 📁 Territorio y medio ambiente
 - 📄 Territorio
 - 📄 Agricultura
- 📁 Cohesión social
 - 📄 Población y demografía
 - 📄 Urbanismo y vivienda
 - 📄 Equipamiento
 - 📄 Procesos electorales
 - 📄 Transporte
 - 📄 Educación
 - 📄 Características, ingresos y gasto de los hogares
- 📁 Economía y competitividad
- 📁 Imagen y turismo
 - 📄 Patrimonio cultural y natural
 - 📄 Hostelería y turismo

Indicadores seleccionados: 0 / 1.045

Sistema Inteligente de Exploración

Esta es una aplicación concebida para la consulta y análisis de un almacén de indicadores. Permite consultar múltiples territorios y diferentes periodos de tiempo. Todos los resultados, tanto gráficos como numéricos podemos guardarlos en diferentes formatos.

Los resultados pueden obtenerse a través de:

- 📄 Tablas multidimensionales personalizables
- 📄 Gráficos de evolución temporal interactivos y personalizables
- 📄 Pirámides de población interactivas y personalizables
- 📄 Mapas temáticos interactivos y personalizables

Está disponible una ayuda más extensa dentro de la aplicación.

En la parte inferior de esta página está disponible una guía rápida de uso.

🏠 Cómo navegar
📄 Hacer una tabla
📄 Hacer un gráfico
📄 Hacer una pirámide
📄 Hacer un mapa
🔍 Buscar indicadores

2. Main Results achieved

Tools that previously didn't exist

<https://www.ruralvida.org/servicios>

RURALVIDA
de la ciudad al pueblo

Inicio Quienes somos Servicios Noticias/Documentos Suscríbete Territorio ADESIMAN Contacto Intranet

Servicios

Ciudadanos
La plataforma posibilita la suscripción de los ciudadanos que tengan inquietudes para formar

Pueblos
La plataforma precisa de una continua actualización que se consigue a través de la

Empresas
La plataforma posibilita la suscripción de empresas que tengan inquietudes para formar

RURALVIDA
de la ciudad al pueblo

PROYECTO "DESAFIO SSPA 2021" SSPA

Polirural

Castilla-La Mancha

GOBIERNO DE ESPAÑA
MINISTERIO DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA Y ALIMENTACIÓN
LEYES 2020

Castilla-La Mancha

PODERO EUROPEO AGRICOLA DE DESARROLLO RURAL

PODERO EUROPEO AGRICOLA DE DESARROLLO RURAL

Polirural

GrupoTragsa
Luzma P. Ferreras, Gerente Polirural

Tragsatec
Unal Reyes

Dirección: Juan Gavalo S/N
Carriascosa del campo
16555 (Cuenca)
Teléfono: 969694020
Email: ruralvidaspa@gmail.com

INTERPRETA TIC

- ACERCA DE...
- MAPA
- CENTRO DE INTERPRETACIÓN (RECORDAMIENTO DE TRABAJOS)
- CENTRO DE INTERPRETACIÓN (COLECCIÓN DE VISITAS)
- VISITA PARQUE ARQUEOLÓGICO (REALIDAD AUMENTADA)
- VISITA POR AVISOS SONOROS (VISITA ACCESIBLE)

2. Main Results achieved

influence change
in policies and/or
attitudes

3. Action Plan alignment and adoption

3. Action Plan alignment and adoption

Integrate measures, actions and KPI of the Action Plan into the Local Development Strategy of LEADER Programme

3. Action Plan alignment and adoption

Continue collecting data for KPI of Monitoring system.

Type of indicators	Policy Challenge	Indicators	Target (2030)
Outputs	Policy challenge 1	0.1.1.1 Number of tourist resources valued	8
	Policy challenge 1	01.1.2 No. of tour packages defined	3
	Policy challenge 1	0.1.1.2 Number of activities organized in Sanabria	96
	Policy ch		5
	Policy ch		4
	Policy ch		160
	Policy ch		160
	Policy ch		10
	Policy ch		200
	Policy ch		80
Outcomes	Policy ch		25
	Policy ch		80.000
	Policy ch		8.000
	Policy ch		4.000
	Policy ch		30
	Policy ch		90%
	Policy ch		170.000
	Policy ch		50%
	Policy ch		50%
	Policy ch		160
	Policy ch		4.000
	Policy ch		30%
	Policy ch		820
Impacts	Policy challenge 1	1.1.1 Average income per inhabitant	25.000
	Policy challenge 2	1.2.1. Educational level of the population of the territory (Middle or Higher Education)	3.000
	Policy challenge 3	1.3.1 Number of self-employed in the territory	5.000
	Policy challenge 3	1.3.2 Employment rate in the territory	66%

3. Action Plan alignment and adoption

Explore more **funding options** from the PoliRural Inventory

Increasing the number of stakeholders to improve their balance

Horizon Europe

THE NEXT EU RESEARCH & INNOVATION PROGRAMME (2021 – 2027)

Interreg

4. Pilot case study

Ségobriga, Spain

Background papers, policies, reports strategies and studies

Statement of Purpose

Foresight Implementation Plan

Drivers' Analysis

Key Policy Challenges

Deep Dives

System Dynamic Modeling

- PDF document
- Translate it into Spanish
- Share with Stakeholders
- Published in LEADER ADESIMAN website

5. Technical tools (Guides)

Tools (Guides)	Planned used
Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)	to face possible new crises arising from external factors in the future
Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)	to help Discussions on how the CAP reform is affecting the territory and its economy should be made at the end of 2023 after a year of application of the new CAP
Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)	support tool in the evaluation of the implementation of the Action Plan
The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change	support tool in the evaluation of the implementation of the Action Plan
D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology	reference document to implement future new action plans

5. Technical tools (TECH)

Regional SDM: SDM will be useful to show new policy makers and new stakeholders the importance of collecting data and the possibilities offered by foresight models in the analysis of public policies.

Semex: analyze the contents of the Social Networks

5. Technical tools (TECH)

Rural Attractiveness Explorer: Test it when completed

Digital Innovation Hub: Stakeholders probably won't use it. Possibly TRAGSA team to consult other apps or tools included

Atlas of Best Practices: Complete with more cases. Stakeholders can consult to inspire entrepreneurship activities, although English is a barrier

Francisco García Urbano
Carrascosa del Campo, Spain

Jesus García Duro
San Lorenzo de la Parrilla, Spain

Maria Cristina Smardui
Carrascosa del Campo, Spain

Óscar Fernández Prat
Carrascosa del Campo, Segóbriga, Spain

